

MERCURY DIALLYL AND ALLYL MERCURIC HALIDES.

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Mercury diallyl is formed as a colourless liquid on reducing allyl mercuric iodide with an aqueous solution of sodium stannite. The compound is somewhat unstable at ordinary temperatures slowly depositing mercury and evolving diallyl. By treatment with bromine in ether solution allyl mercuric bromide (m.p. 124-125°) is obtained. By the action of 4% hydrochloric acid on mercury diallyl, allyl mercuric chloride (m.p. 102-103°) has been prepared.

Zinin (*Annalen*, 1855, **96**, 363) prepared allyl mercuric iodide by shaking together mercury and allyl iodide in alcohol with a trace of iodine. Recently Austin (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, **58**, 3514) prepared lead triphenylallyl.

Several workers have attempted to prepare mercury diallyl from allyl mercuric iodide without success. Zinin states that C_3H_5HgI heated just above its melting point (134-35°) decomposes giving a gaseous product, (which he did not identify) leaving behind a carbonaceous residue. The preparation of mercury diallyl was, therefore, first attempted by the action of heat on C_3H_5HgI .

EXPERIMENTAL.

Purified allyl mercuric iodide (60 g.) from acetone was placed in an all glass distillation apparatus. After displacing the air by dry hydrogen and evacuating to about 1 mm., the substance was slowly heated in a paraffin oil-bath. Decomposition occurred at about 120°. The distillate (5-6 c.c.) consisted of a mixture of allyl iodide and diallyl. The residue consisted of mercurous iodide and free mercury only. The reactions are probably represented by the following equations :

Allyl mercuric iodide was heated with an excess of potassium iodide in an all glass apparatus at about 1 mm. pressure, the residual gas being hydrogen, as before. Decomposition occurred at about 115°. The distillate was found to be again allyl iodide and diallyl, and the residue contained K_2HgI_4 and free mercury.

The above results suggest that mercury diallyl may be formed as an intermediate product but it decomposes at the temperature of the reaction,

The formation of K_2HgI_4 in the last experiment and the nearly equivalent amounts of free mercury and diallyl (*cf.* Oppenheim, *Ber.*, 1871, 4, 671) lend support to this conjecture. Hence reagents which act on organomercuric compounds in the cold and bring about "condensation" were next tried (Whitmore, "Organic Compounds of Mercury," p. 59). Sodium thiosulphate and alkaline sulphide solutions were found to have only very slight action on C_3H_5HgI , and the black insoluble products were only inorganic mercury compounds, and the solution appeared to contain no new organomercuric compound.

When strongly alkaline solution of sodium stannite was added to C_3H_5HgI suspended in water (*cf.* Dimroth, *Chem. Zentr.*, 1901, I, 451; Whitmore, *loc. cit.*, p. 63), mercury separated immediately and an oily liquid with a very offensive smell was formed. The oily liquid was extracted with ether, the ethereal solution dried over $CaCl_2$, and the ether distilled off. A clear colourless liquid with a nauseating odour was obtained.

This product contains Hg, C and H, and it burns with a luminous flame forming yellow fumes of HgO . It is not spontaneously inflammable nor does it oxidise very rapidly in air, but mercury separates on standing at room temperature ($30-35^\circ$). The liquid cannot be distilled even in nitrogen at less than 1 mm. pressure as it decomposes into mercury and diallyl.

The compound, freed from ether as far as possible, becomes viscous when cooled with ice and salt but it crystallises in long needles with solid carbon dioxide. It crystallises from ethereal solutions also when cooled with carbon dioxide snow. Attempts were made to purify the substance by crystallisation from ether at low temperatures using a specially designed all glass apparatus in a moisture-free nitrogen atmosphere. In each case, however, mercury began to separate before the last traces of ether had been removed. The composition of the substance, while still containing traces of ether, was determined and derivatives prepared.

Samples of the purest preparations obtained were drawn into weighed capillaries, before separation of mercury set in and analysed. The mercury was weighed as $HgCr_2O_7$, $2C_5H_5N$, and the carbon and hydrogen were estimated by the ordinary methods. [Found : C, 26.37; H, 3.92; Hg, 70.1. $Hg(C_3H_5)_2$ requires C, 25.49; H, 3.567; Hg, 70.99 per cent]. These results are low for mercury and rather high for C and H owing to traces of ether present. They are, however, sufficiently accurate to show that the substance is mercury diallyl. The yield is nearly quantitative.

Mercury diallyl is soluble in ether, benzene and carbon disulphide but it is insoluble in absolute alcohol. On heating in a sealed tube in an atmosphere of nitrogen it decomposes into mercury and diallyl. Its density is 2.7.

On coming in contact with the skin, it causes painful blisters after a few hours. Even in red light it slowly decomposes depositing mercury. A moderately concentrated solution keeps for a few hours and it was used for the reactions described below.

Mercury dialkyls react with halogens, halogen hydracids, and mercuric halides as in

(Whitmore, "Organic Compounds of Mercury," Ch. III and Newton Friend, "Text Book of Inorganic Chemistry" Vol. XI, Goddard and Goddard, Ch. III). So if the substance is $\text{Hg}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_5)_2$, these reagents would all be expected to give $\text{C}_3\text{H}_5\text{HgI}$.

An alcoholic solution of iodide gave an immediate precipitate of glistening white crystals turning yellow on exposure to light. Recrystallised from alcohol they melted with partial decomposition at 133° and gave with Na_2SnO_2 the same liquid with the unpleasant smell. Very dilute HI also gave $\text{C}_3\text{H}_5\text{HgI}$ dissolving in excess. HgI_2 also gave $\text{C}_3\text{H}_5\text{HgI}$, though in very small yield.

Action of Bromine on Mercury Diallyl: Preparation of Allyl Mercuric Bromide.—Mercury diallyl inflames with liquid bromine. An ethereal solution of bromine gives a white shining crystalline precipitate. This product crystallises from alcohol in transparent silvery plates, melting with partial decomposition at $124\text{--}25^\circ$. It sublimes at about 95° . (Found: C, 11.11; H, 1.53; Br, 25.04; Hg, 62.1. $\text{C}_3\text{H}_5\text{HgBr}$ requires C, 11.2; H, 1.568; Br, 24.86; Hg, 62.4 per cent.) $\text{C}_3\text{H}_5\text{HgBr}$ is soluble in ether, acetone, carbon disulphide and benzene. By the action of Na_2SnO_2 , $\text{Hg}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_5)_2$ is formed. Very dilute HBr, excess of which is to be avoided, and also alcoholic HgBr_2 react with $\text{Hg}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_5)_2$ to form $\text{C}_3\text{H}_5\text{Hg Br}$.

Preparation of Allyl Mercuric Chloride.—Mercury diallyl inflames when dropped into chlorine gas. With chlorine in carbon tetrachloride it gives an insoluble white compound which appears to be mercurous compound. Alcoholic HgCl_2 also gives a similar insoluble compound. Allyl mercuric chloride was prepared by the action of approximately 4% HCl on $\text{Hg}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_5)_2$. $\text{C}_3\text{H}_5\text{HgCl}$ crystallises from alcohol, in glistening plates, melting with partial decomposition at $102\text{--}103^\circ$. (Found: C, 13.22; H, 1.89; Cl, 12.82; Hg, 72.4. $\text{C}_3\text{H}_5\text{HgCl}$ requires C, 12.99; H, 1.819; Cl, 12.79; Hg, 72.38 per cent.) It sublimes above 80° . It is soluble in acetone, ether, carbon disulphide, benzene and aqueous alcohol. Na_2SnO_2

solution gives $\text{Hg}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_5)_2$. The action of HCl on $\text{Hg}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_5)_2$ may be represented by

The gas evolved was identified as propylene. Bromination yields propylene dibromide, b.p. 142° . Strong solutions of HCl react with $\text{C}_3\text{H}_5\text{HgCl}$ as

which is similar to the action of strong HI on $\text{C}_3\text{H}_5\text{HgI}$, (*cf.* Linnemann, *Annalen Suppl.*, 1865, 3, 262).

An interesting gradation of properties is observed in the three allyl mercuric halides. The chloride, bromide and iodide melt with partial decomposition at $102\text{-}3^\circ$, $124\text{-}25^\circ$, and $133\text{-}35^\circ$ respectively. They sublime at about 80° , 95° , and 100° respectively. Solubility in various solvents and stability towards light decrease from the chloride to the iodide. The chloride remains undecomposed without giving any smell even after weeks, whereas the iodide is turned yellow rapidly on exposure to light and gives off a penetrating smell, indicating partial decomposition, on keeping in the dark for a few hours. The bromide gives traces of insoluble matter on keeping for a few weeks indicating partial decomposition.

Potassium permanganate solution acts on mercury dialkyls forming the hydroxides (Seidel, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1814, 291, 135)

$\text{Hg}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_5)_2$ decolourises KMnO_4 precipitating MnO_2 , but the filtrate does not contain $\text{C}_3\text{H}_5\text{HgOH}$, for, with halogen hydracids, it does not give allyl mercuric halides nor does it give mercury diallyl with Na_2SiO_2 .

Probably the solution contains γ -hydroxymercuripropylenglycol obtained by the oxidation of the double bond at the same time as the oxidation of the mercury diallyl. The salts of this base are known (*cf.* Whitmore, "Organic Compounds of Mercury," p. 133).

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